

Reactions of Coordinated Oximes—Part V : Reactions of Aluminium Isopropoxide on Some Cobalt(II) *Bis*-Chelates of *o*-Hydroxy Oximes

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Cobalt(II) *bis*-chelates of some *o*-hydroxyketoximes have been prepared and characterised by analytical and magnetic susceptibility measurements. They form planar *bis*-chelates with cobalt(II) ions. The further reactions of these cobalt(II) *bis*-chelates with aluminium isopropoxide have been carried out and were studied by analytical and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The tetraisopropoxy derivatives are proposed to have a six-coordinate tetragonal structure.

STUDIES on the metal-chelates of the oxime ligands are important in view of their possible applications as biological models^{1,2} and as semi-conducting materials^{3,4}. Also, the *bis*-chelates of the vic-dioximes and *o*-hydroxyoximes involve short inter-ligand hydrogen bond and packing configurations which give rise to unusual optical properties. The protons involved in the inter-ligand hydrogen bonding are labile and are suitable for the reactions with a variety of reagent. The reactions of boron halides⁵ and some organoaluminium compounds⁶ with nickel(II) and palladium(II) *bis*-chelates of dimethylglyoxime and salicylaldoxime have been reported.

In continuation to our work⁷⁻¹⁰ on reactions of metal alkoxides on coordinated oximes we report in this paper the reactions of aluminium isopropoxide on cobalt(II) *bis*-chelates of some *ortho*-hydroxy oximes viz.,

- (i) 2-hydroxy benzaldoxime (salH₂), Ia ;
- (ii) 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldoxime (vanH₂), Ib ;
- (iii) 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenoneoxime (hmaH₂), Ic ;
- (iv) 2-hydroxy-5-methyl propiophenoneoxime (hmpH₂), Id, and
- (v) 2-hydroxy-5-methyl butyrophenoneoxime (hmbH₂), Ie

(I)

- (a) X=H, R=H
- (b) X=3-OCH₃, R=H
- (c) X=5-CH₃, R=CH₃
- (d) X=5-CH₃, R=C₂H₅
- (e) X=5-CH₃, R=C₄H₉

In all the cases the bridging protons are replaced by Al(OPr)₂ groups. Also cobalt achieves six-coordination through axial coordination by the propoxide groups.

Experimental

Aluminium isopropoxide was obtained¹¹ by the reaction of isopropanol on aluminium foil in presence of catalyst (HgCl₂) and was purified by distillation at reduced pressure at ~110°. The ligands were prepared by the literature method¹². The *bis*-chelates were prepared by mixing aqueous solution of metal salts and alcoholic solution of the respective ligands in molar ratio 2 : 1 and adjusting the pH to ~6.0 with sodium acetate. In all cases the complexes separated out and were filtered, washed with water and 50% alcohol and dried in an electric oven.

Reactions of cobalt(II) bis-chelates with aluminium isopropoxide : A benzene solution of aluminium isopropoxide was added to the cobalt(II) *bis*-chelates in 2 : 1 molar ratio in each case. On refluxing the contents the following colour changes were observed :

- Co(salH)₂ - from brown to dark brown,
Co(vanH)₂ - from orange to brown,
Co(hmaH)₂ - from yellow to dark brown,
Co(hmpH)₂ - from yellow to dark brown, and
Co(hmbH)₂ - from yellow to dark brown.

Refluxing in all the cases was continued for about 6 hr. The benzene-propanol azeotrope was collected (72°) and analysed for propanol content. The excess solvent was removed first by distillation at atmospheric pressure and then under reduced pressure. The reaction product was finally dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

The alcohol contents were determined by indirect iodometric titration with potassium dichromate and cobalt contents were determined by titration against standard EDTA solution using xylenol orange as indicator.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements on solid complexes were made by Gouy method using tetracyanatoncobaltate as calibrant ($\chi_M = 16.44 \times 10^6$ cgs units).

TABLE 1—COLOUR, COMPOSITION AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF TETRAISOPROPOXY DERIVATIVES OF COBALT(II) COMPLEXES

Reactants	Molar ratio	Product, state and colour	Benzene + propanol azeotropy Found (Calcd.)	Elemental analysis Found (Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	
				%N	%Al	%Co	Benzene	Solid
Co(salH) ₂ + Al(OPr ^t) ₃ (3.09 g) + (2.62 g)	1 : 2	Co[sal.Al(OPr ^t) ₂] ₂ , solid, dark brown	0.74 (0.77)	4.48 (4.52)	8.62 (8.73)	9.41 (9.52)	*	3.61
Co(vanH) ₂ + Al(OPr ^t) ₃ (2.42 g) + (2.52 g)	1 : 2	Co(van.Al(OPr ^t) ₂) ₂ , solid, dark brown	0.71 (0.74)	4.02 (4.12)	7.72 (7.95)	8.50 (8.68)	*	3.49
Co(hmaH) ₂ + Al(OPr ^t) ₃ (2.92 g) + (3.07 g)	1 : 2	Co[hma.Al(OPr ^t) ₂] ₂ , solid, dark brown	0.86 (0.90)	4.28 (4.15)	8.12 (8.00)	8.61 (8.78)	3.83	3.42
Co(hmpH) ₂ + Al(OPr ^t) ₃ (2.52 g) + (2.47 g)	1 : 2	Co[hmp.Al(OPr ^t) ₂] ₂ , solid, dark brown	0.70 (0.72)	3.67 (3.98)	7.59 (7.68)	8.19 (8.38)	3.82	3.41
Co(hmbH) ₂ + Al(OPr ^t) ₃ (2.62 g) + (2.41 g)	1 : 2	Co[hmb.Al(OPr ^t) ₂] ₂ , solid, dark brown	0.68 (0.70)	3.70 (3.88)	7.29 (7.88)	8.00 (8.06)	3.87	3.58

* The compounds are insoluble.

Results and Discussion

The bis-chelates show room temperature magnetic moments of 2.2-2.3 B.M. corresponding to planar cobalt(II). Bis-chelates of the ortho-hydroxyoximes are known^{1,2} to have planar structure (II) which derives extra stability from additional rings formed through inter-ligand hydrogen bonding.

The stoichiometry of the reaction with Al(OPr^t)₃ is shown in Table 1. Analysis of benzene propanol azeotrope in all the cases correspond to the reaction of two moles of aluminium isopropoxide with one mole of metal chelate yielding two moles of propanol. This stoichiometry is shown in reaction (1) abbreviating all the six ligands as LH₂.

The two inter-ligand hydrogen bridges of Co(LH)₂ are replaced by two Al(OPr^t)₃ groups. All the compounds give consistent analysis for Co[L-Al(OPr^t)₂]₂.

The reaction products show magnetic moment of 3.4-3.5 B.M. in solid state and 3.8-3.9 B.M. in benzene solutions (wherever soluble). These values suggest that the square-planar geometry of the parent chelate is not retained. Obtaining of six-coordinate tetragonal structure by involving the terminal isopropoxy groups into coordination seems to be the most plausible interpretation to the observed magnetic moments. For such a geometry, cobalt(II) complexes (ground state ⁴T_{1g}) should show^{1,4} magnetic moments corresponding to three unpaired spins. The experimental values are known to lie upto 5.0 due to spin orbit coupling. Sub-normal magnetic moments in the present compounds are obtained due to spin-coupling between

two cobalt atoms through the O-Al-O bridges (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The complexes react with water to convert into tetrahydroxo species with release of isopropanol as shown below :

But the tetrahydroxo species are very much stable and do not break into the parent chelates even on boiling with water. This extra stability of tetraisopropoxy derivatives to the corresponding nickel(II) derivatives may be attributed to the stable cage formed through the O-Co-O-Al-O-Co-O bridges.

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INDRA RANI, PANDEYA & SINGH : REACTIONS OF COORDINATED OXIMES—PART V

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